

EVALUATION OF COMBINED EFFECTS OF AGING TREATMENT (DRY AGING AND WET AGING) AND BREED ON QUALITY ATTRIBUTES OF LOCALLY MARKETED RED MEAT

SARA BENSOUA *

Research Laboratory, Biotechnology applied to Agriculture and Environmental Preservation, Higher School of Agronomy of Mostaganem, Algeria. *Corresponding Author Email: s.bensoula@esa-mosta.dz

MOHAMED ELAFFIFI

Research Laboratory, Biotechnology applied to Agriculture and Environmental Preservation, Higher School of Agronomy of Mostaganem, Algeria.

SAMIRA BECILA

Institute of Food Nutrition and Agro-Food Technologies (INATAA), Mentouri Brothers University of Constantine 1, Algeria. Email: s.bensoula@esa-mosta.dz

Abstract

The purpose of this work is to know the effect of using two types of aging and two breeds on the moisture maintain capacity of locally marketed red meat. Two groups of (n=30) of red meat samples were collected from Algerian beef and lamb carcasses slaughtered under appropriate conditions, with a selection of three types of muscle (n=10): Supraspinatus, Longissimus Dorsi and Semimembranosus. Half of each group was aged in carcass (Dry aging 24 to 36 h after slaughter before storage at $18 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$), while the other half was wet matured (Vacuum sealed directly after slaughter and stored for 24h at $4 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ to avoid cold shortening before kept at $18 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$). In addition to the pH measurement [1], analysis such as water holding capacity (WHC), cooking loss (CL), drip loss (DL) and thawing loss (TL) were measured using [2] modified by [3], [4], [5] and [6] respectively to estimate the level of moisture loss in the samples studied. pH measurement showed that dry aged samples have significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher pH level 5.56 ± 0.20 comparatively to the wet aged ones 5.46 ± 0.20 . Regarding Water-Holding Capacity level. Results showed no significant difference between the two types of aging used: wet aging and dry aging with values of $19.02\% \pm 0.05$ vs $19.29\% \pm 0.06$ respectively. And the same goes for the percentage of relegated water. Where the results were almost equal with $32.68\% \pm 0.07$ in dry aged samples and $32.56\% \pm 0.06$ in wet aged ones. Moreover. this is also the case for cooking loss level where mean results show no difference between dry aged $37.45\% \pm 0.04$ and wet aged $36.33\% \pm 0.04$ samples. Therefore. Dry aged samples had significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower drip losses $2.46\% \pm 0.01$ comparatively to the wet aged ones $3.32\% \pm 0.01$. as well as for thawing losses that were significantly and remarkably ($p < 0.05$) high in the samples that were aged in vacuum sealed $4.78\% \pm 0.01$ by comparison to those aged traditionally (dry aged) $3.26\% \pm 0.01$.

Keywords: Conservation, Dry Aging, Red Meat, Water Loss, Wet Aging.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that many factors change during post-mortem, but moisture content in red meat is considered as the most important one especially by the industry because of its economic implication on the yield. And because water occupies a large percentage of the meat weight, the moisture retain capacity of the muscle is crucial to maintain other meat qualities that both the industry and the consumer highly value.

Moisture loss is a result of many changes acting during rigor mortis and conditioning such as pH reduction, ATP loss, and the steric impacts (result of the shrinkage of the

myofibrillar) [7]. These changes can occur either separately or collectively to release protein-bound water to the extracellular and sarcoplasmic spaces.

On top of moisture loss, a rapid post-mortem pH drop can cause permanent problems mainly protein denaturation, that in its turn affect the technological and sensory qualities (Water retention capacity, colour, texture or tenderness) of the meat [8].

Generally talking, Water holding capacity is considered as muscle capability to retrain any moisture either its own water or any added liquid during other treatments [9]. However, this capacity can easily be influenced by many factors at different stages: During the growth of meat animals (Genotype and diet), in the immediate pre-slaughter period (Stresses), or in the post-slaughter period (Chilling, aging, injecting non-meat ingredients, tumbling) [10].

In contrary, drip loss refers to the highly protein-rich fluid lost from the meat without any addition of fluid or mechanical force except gravity [9]. In addition to the protein waste, the lost fluid may contain iron [11]. This problem can be contributed by Post-mortem protein degradation and/or Desmin degradation during storage [12]. In addition to affecting the already mentioned qualities (sensory and technological), high drip loss is more serious because it affects the nutritional value and the palatability of the meat, thereby it causes a real problem for meat industry professionals to preserve the meat and keep its quality and acceptability [13].

Moreover, further processing such as cooking and freezing can also affect the moisture content of the meat, considering: methods used, cooking/freezing rate, cooking and endpoint temperature [10]. For this reason, cooking loss became of interest to explain both the variation in juiciness and the appearance of the meat during cooking, it is therefore expected to have less of a mediocre eating quality when cooking loss is high [14].

The fluid lost after freezing and thawing due to the exudate formation is called thawing loss [15]. Ice crystals formed inside cells during freezing period puncture the wall of these cells resulting in fluid leakage when thawing.

Thawing loss has also a significant effect on the sensory and instrumental quality of the meat due to fat and protein oxidation, caused by the release of pro-oxidative enzymes during cell wall puncture [16].

The objective of this study was to investigate how moisture loss depends on the aging treatment and the race of the meat and whether there is an interaction between the two. On this background, it was aimed to investigate how moisture loss influenced the quality of meat depending on the aging treatment to increase the understanding of this attribute.

2. MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Samples Preparation

Two groups of 30 lamb and 30 beef used in this study came from different Algerian producers to ensure a certain heterogeneity of our results. all these carcasses were intended for local marketing.

After slaughter, three different muscle types were collected (samples of 250g): Supraspinatus (SS) corresponding to the brisket, Longissimus Dorsi (LD) corresponding to the fillets and Semimembranosus (SM) corresponding to the leg due to their preference by the consumer.

Half of each group was aged traditionally in carcass (Dry aging) for 24 to 36 h after slaughter before packed and stored at $-18 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. While the other half was aged in vacuum-sealed bags (Wet aging) just after the slaughter in refrigerator for 24 hours at $4 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ to avoid cold shortening then stored at $-18 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$.

2.2 Ph Value

To measure the meat pH value, we used a method based on that described by [1], in which 1g of muscle was taken and placed in a tube containing 10 ml of sodium iodoacetate buffer (5mM), and potassium chloride (150mM) adjusted to pH 7.0. Then the sample was homogenized using a homogenizer (Polytron ® PT- MR 2100, Kinematica AG, Switzerland) for 15 to 25 seconds. The pH result was read, using a pH meter previously calibrated (model

pH.mV.Temp). the operation is repeated three times and the results are expressed in Mean \pm SD.

2.3 Water Holding Capacity (Whc) and Percentage of Relegated Water

In order to evaluate the water holding capacity (WHC) and the percentage of relegated water (PRW), we referred to the method of [2] modified by [3], also known as "Filter Paper Press Method", based on a compression principle. For this protocol, a filter paper with the following characteristics (Weight = \approx 0.22g; Diameter = 6cm) was dried in the oven at $37 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 7 min and then preserved in a desiccator to prevent moisture absorption. The paper is then weighed in the dry state (P), before adding meat. Then 300 mg 5 of meat (G) is deposited on the filter paper. The whole is inserted between two glass plates and then a weight of 2.25kg is placed above for 5 min, after this given moment, the areas of compressed meat (M) and relegated juice (T) appear in the form of circles that are reported on a transparent plastic paper. The areas of circle of meat (M) and liquid (T) were measured using the software «Image J 1.48» expressed in mm or pixel. The last remaining step is to calculate the relegated water, and to do so we removed the compressed meat and the wet filter paper (D) was weighted, the results are then expressed in percentage. Three tests were conducted for each sample.

2.4 Drip Loss

To determine drip losses in our samples we opted for the method described by [5]. Briefly, two pieces ((weight \approx 6 g; diameter 30 mm; height 35 mm each) were removed from each

meat sample using EZ-drip loss circular knives. The meat cores were removed following the fibre orientation then placed in a special EZ container before being weighted (P), and stored in a refrigerator at an average temperature of $4 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for a period of 48 hours. Before re-weighting (P'), the samples were gently wiped with paper towel [17]. The EZ drip loss was expressed in percentage relative to the initial weight.

2.5 Cooking Loss

The evaluation of water losses during cooking is based on the measurement of the ratio between the weight of a piece of meat before and after cooking. This is carried out according to the method described by [4], where the piece of muscle taken was weighed (P), and placed in impermeable plastic bags previously identified, and sealed with a heat welder, then immersed in a water bath at a constant temperature of $80 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour. After cooking, the plastic bags are emptied and the meat samples are lightly wiped with paper towels and weighed again (P'). The difference between the two weights determines the losses of water during cooking, which are expressed in percentage; three tests are carried out for each sample.

2.6 Thawing Loss

The frozen samples were removed for the thawing treatments and weighted (P) before being thawed. Thawing method used was carried out in bags emerged in a water bath at $4 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ in a refrigeration unit with minimal air flow until the thawing was considered complete (internal temperature $\approx 4^\circ\text{C}$) [6]. Before reweighting (P'), samples were blotting dry with a paper towel. Thaw loss was then determined by calculating the difference between the two weights. Thaw loss was found in percentage of initial weight.

3. RESULTS

The results found concerning pH value, water holding capacity percentage (WHC), relegated water percentage (PRW), cooking loss (CL), drip loss (DL), and thawing loss (TL) are resumed in Table 1.

Table 1: Means \pm standard error of the mean (SEM) (n=36) of pH, WHC, PRW, CL, DL, and TL of studied samples classified by breed and aging treatment

	Dry aged samples (n=18)	Wet aged samples (n=18)
pH	5.56 \pm 0.20	5.46 \pm 0.20
WHC (%)	19.29 \pm 0.06	19.02 \pm 0.05
PRW (%)	32.68 \pm 0.07	32.56 \pm 0.06
CL (%)	37.45 \pm 0.04	36.33 \pm 0.04
DL (%)	2.46 \pm 0.01	3.32 \pm 0.01
TL (%)	3.26 \pm 0.01	4.78 \pm 0.01

Source: Own Elaboration

pH: Hydrogen Potential, WHC: Water Holding Capacity, PRW: Percentage of Relegated Water, CL: Cooking Loss, DL: Drip Loss, TL: Thawing Loss.

reduced just before the slaughter due to a number prerequisite (stress, transport, pain...) that are factors worth to consider that can easily lead to high pH phenomenon.

On the same page as [21], [22], [23], we found that dry aged samples proceed quite a high pH value compared to the wet aged ones, and that can maybe be explained by the presence of nitrogen compounds from proteolysis during aging treatment [21].

Clearly, we observed that pH values were significantly ($p < 0.05$) more acidic in dry aged lamb samples in comparison to the beef ones presented in Fig 1, but both were in the standards since [24], [25] and [26] estimate that pH values below 6 do not have a negative impact on meat quality. On the other hand, we observed no influence of the breed on pH values of wet aged samples as shown in Fig 2.

The values obtained from WHC are between a minimum value of 11.51% and a maximum value of 37.29% for dry aged samples versus a minimum value of 11.52% and a maximum value of 27.43% for wet aged samples presented in Table 1. However, there is no influence neither of the type of aging treatment or the breed on the mean results of WHC, in contrary of [23] results who clearly found a difference. But in comparison to our results, these latter were way low with a mean of $19.02\% \pm 0.05$ vs $19.29\% \pm 0.06$ in wet aging and dry aging respectively. Low WHC are often caused by a rapid drop in final meat pH, which as already mentioned is due to a combination of factors such as genetics, pre and post slaughter conditions handling [27]. Changes in polypeptide conformation of myofibrillary proteins such as formation of intramolecular bridges due to divalent cations (Ca^{2+} , K^{+} and Mg^{2+}) can result to a reduction in water holding capacity [18], [28]. The decreased WHC of DA samples might be because of low moisture content caused by evaporation during dry aging. These previous explanations can also be applied on the percentage of relegated water results found for both dry and wet aged samples as seen in Fig 3.

Figure 3: Means \pm standard error (n=36) of Relegated Water Percentage by aging Treatment and by Breed

DA: Dry aged; WA: Wet aged; PRW: Percentage of relegated water. Source: Own elaboration

The average loss when cooking dry aged meat (DA) is $37.45\% \pm 0.04$ varying from a minimum value of 28.39% to 47.21%, and when cooking wet aged meat (WA) the loss was $36.33\% \pm 0.04$ varying from 30.72% to 42.48% shown in Fig 4. This parameter differs depending on several factors such as: cooking time, cooking temperature, cold storage time, anatomical muscle location, and race.

Figure 4: Means \pm Standard error (n=36) of Cooking Loss Values in % of dry and Wet Aged Samples

DA: Dry aged; WA: Wet aged; CL: Cooking loss. Source: Own elaboration

Our results were much higher than [29] in both dry and wet aged samples ($\approx 20.90 \pm 3.45$), but very similar to those found by [30].

In contrary to [31], our samples were not affected by the type of aging treatment used (dry and wet aged meat) and that can be because the ejected water during cooking is mainly coming from chemically bound water (10% of the total fluid) and the melted fat [32]. In this respect, the contraction of muscle fibres and intramuscular connective tissue is the major cause leading to cooking loss during thermal treatment, taking into consideration the temperature and method used. This contraction extent largely depends on the temperature [33] that at first causes a denaturation of the myofibrillar proteins before coagulating them, which cause by consequent myofilaments lattice shrinkage, the main reason of fluid loss, toughness and dryness of the meat [34]. No significant influence of the race (Lamb/Beef) was seen on the results found.

The drip losses values obtained vary from a minimum value of 1.02% and maximum of 5.21% for all dry aged meat tested, with an average mean value of $3.26\% \pm 0.01$. Whilst, we obtained a mean value of drip loss of $4.78\% \pm 0.01$ in wet aged meat with values that range from 3.66% to 6.84% summarized in table 1.

Figure 5: Means ± standard error (n=36) of drip loss values in % of dry and wet Aged Samples

DA: Dry aged; WA: Wet aged; DL: Drip loss. Source: Own elaboration

Drip loss (fluid loss during display) of the meat is important, especially since it plays a crucial role to attract and appeal to the consumer to buy it [6]. To explain how a meat can lose fluid during storage, it is worth noting that drip losses are caused mainly by a set of changes in myofibril lattice spacing but also the direction of the muscle fibres during storage have a huge influence on the level of these losses [25], [35].

Our results showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) difference in drip losses between dry and wet aged meat, where vacuum sealed aged meat lost almost 0.7 times more fluid than dry aged meat. High level of drip losses can be related to a rapid post-mortem glycolysis and pH drop, associated with poor water holding capacity and pale color [36]. Studies have reported that the dry aging process results in an up to 10% of drip loss [31]. The increase in drip loss observed in Fig 5 can be related to the loss of the ability of the water to interact with proteins leading to accelerate the movement of water from the intracellular to the extracellular space. Moving out of the meat through the enlarged drip loss channels formed during the shrinkage [7]. No significant influence of the race (Lamb/Beef) was seen on the results found.

Dry aging reduced thawing loss with a mean value of $3.26\% \pm 0.01$ in comparison to the wet aged samples who revealed a thawing loss of $4.78\% \pm 0.01$ shown in Table 1. Breed have no significant influence on the amount of fluid lost during thawing. Wet aged samples showing more thawing loss can be explained by their no capacity to lose water during aging by evaporation (dehydration). Less shrinkage is observed when vacuum-sealed. Ambrosiadis et al [37] declared that thawing increases the drip loss and it is at the maximum value in refrigerated thawing (More than 24 h).

5. CONCLUSION

The aim of this study was to find the effect of a combination of different aging treatments (dry and wet aging) and different breed (Beef and lamb) on the quality of red meat locally marketed.

From the results of the present study, it may be concluded that, different aging treatments was found to have no significant influence on any of the quality parameters tested, except on the drip and thawing loss. In terms of the aging method, the outcomes also confirmed that dry aging process induced an improvement in moisture holding capacity and therefore in tenderness and sensory characteristics of red meat. The present study demonstrated also that all quality parameters tested (cooking losses, water holding capacity, drip loss, thawing loss) are not affected by the breed.

References

- 1) McGeehin. B, Sheridan. J. J, Butler. F (2001), Factors affecting the pH decline in lamb after slaughter. 6 pages , Meat Science 58 (2001) 79±84
- 2) Grau R., Hamm R. (1953). A simple method for the determination of water binding in muscles. *Naturwissenschaften* 40, 29-30.
- 3) Hafid Kahina, Mohammed Gagaoua, Samira becila, Abdelghani Boudjellal (2015). Vers une nouvelle approche par traitement d'image pour la mesure de la capacite de rétention d'eau de la viande.
- 4) Pascual M., Pla M. (2007). Changes in carcass composition and meat quality when selecting rabbits for growth rate. *Meat science*, 77(4), 474-481.
- 5) Rasmussen A.J., Andersson M. (September 1996) New method for determination of drip loss in pork muscles; Proceedings of the 42nd International Congress of Meat Science and Technology; Lillehammer, 1–6; pp. 286–287.
- 6) Leygonie, C.; Hoffman, L.C. (2020) Effect of Different Combinations of Freezing and Thawing Rates on the Shelf-Life and Oxidative Stability of Ostrich Moon Steaks (*M. Femorotibialis medius*) under Retail Display Conditions. *Foods*, 9, 1624. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9111624>
- 7) E. Huff-Lonergan and S. M. Lonergan, (2005) Mechanisms of water-holding capacity of meat: the role of postmortem biochemical and structural changes," *Meat Science*, vol. 71, no. 1, pp. 194–204.
- 8) LEBRET, B., & PICARD, B. (2015). Les principales composantes de la qualité des carcasses et des viandes dans les différentes espèces animales. *INRAE Productions Animales*, 28(2), 93–98. <https://doi.org/10.20870/productions-animales.2015.28.2.3013>
- 9) Huff-Lonergan, E. (2009). Fresh meat water-holding capacity. In *Improving the Sensory and Nutritional Quality of Fresh Meat*. <https://doi.org/10.1533/9781845695439.1.147>
- 10) Cheng Q, Sun DW. (2008) Factors affecting the water holding capacity of red meat products: a review of recent research advances. *Crit Rev Food Sci Nutr*; 48(2):137-59. doi: 10.1080/10408390601177647. PMID: 18274969.
- 11) Ponsuksili S, Murani E, Phatsara C, Jonas E, Walz C, Schwerin M *et al.* (2008). Expression profiling of muscle reveals transcripts differentially expressed in muscle that affect water-holding capacity of pork. *J Agric Food Chem* 56: 10311–10317
- 12) Muhan Zhang, Daoying Wang, Xinglian Xu, Weimin Xu, (2019) Comparative proteomic analysis of proteins associated with water holding capacity in goose muscles, *Food Research International*, Volume 116, Pages 354-361,
- 13) Forrest, J.C., M.T. Morgan, C. Borggaard, A.J. Rasmussen, B.L. Jespersen, and J.R. Andersen. (2000). Development of technology for the early post mortem prediction of water holding capacity, and drip loss in fresh pork. *Meat Science*, 55(1), 115-122.
- 14) Aaslyng, Margit & Bejerholm, Camilla & Ertbjerg, Per & Bertram, Hanne & Andersen, Henrik. (2003). Cooking loss and juiciness of pork in relation to raw meat quality and cooking procedure. *Food Quality and Preference*. 14. 277-288. 10.1016/S0950-3293(02)00086-1.

- 15) Yu, L. H., Lee, E. S., Jeong, J. Y., Paik, H. D., Choi, J. H. & Kim, C. J. (2005). Effects of thawing temperature on the physicochemical properties of pre-rigor frozen chicken breast and leg muscles. *Meat Sci.* 71, 375- 382.
- 16) Leygonie C., Britz T. J., Hoffman L. C. (2012). Meat quality comparison between fresh and frozen/thawed ostrich *M. iliofibularis*. *Meat Sci.*
- 17) J. A. Correa, S. Méthot, and L. Faucitano, , (2007) A modified meat juice container (EZ-DripLoss) procedure for a more reliable assessment of Drip Loss and related quality changes in pork meat," *Journal of Muscle Foods*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 67–77.
- 18) Offer, G., Knight, P. (1988). The structural basis of WHC in meat. In: *Develop. Meat Sci.- 4*. Lawrie R.A. éd., P7
- 19) Vilella, Gustavo & Lugnani, Carolina & Battaglia, Christian & Pacheco, Maria Teresa & Silva, Vera & Rodas-González, Argenis & Pflanzler, Sérgio. (2019). Effects of combined wet- and dry-aging techniques on the physicochemical and sensory attributes of beef ribeye steaks from grain-fed crossbred Zebu steers. *Canadian Journal of Animal Science*. 99. 10.1139/CJAS-2018-0127.
- 20) Koutsoumanis, Kostas & Misiou, Ourania & Kakagianni, Myrsini. (2022). Climate change threatens the microbiological stability of non-refrigerated foods. *Food Research International*. 162. 111990. 10.1016/j.foodres.2022.111990.
- 21) Aksu MI, Kaya M, Ockerman HW. (2005) Effect of modified atmosphere packaging and temperature on the shelf life of sliced pastirma produced from frozen/thawed meat. *J Muscle Foods*. 16:192–206. doi: 10.1111/j.1745-4573.2005.08404.x.
- 22) Kim M, Choe J, Lee HJ, Yoon Y, Yoon S and Jo C, (2019). Effects of aging and aging method on physicochemical and sensory traits of different beef cuts. *Food Science of Animal Resources*, 39, 54–64.
- 23) Kim JH, Kim TK, Shin DM, Kim HW, Kim YB and Choi YS, (2020). Comparative effects of dry aging and wet aging on physicochemical properties and digestibility of Hanwoo beef. *Asian-Australasian Journal of Animal Sciences*, 33, 501–505.
- 24) Mach, N., Bach, A., Velarde, A., & Devant, M. (2008). Association between animal, transportation, slaughterhouse practices, and meat pH in beef. *Meat Science*, 78(3), 232– 238. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2007.06.021>
- 25) Hughes, J. M., Oiseth, S. K., Purslow, P. P., & Warner, R. D. (2014). A structural approach to understanding the interactions between colour, water-holding capacity and tenderness. *Meat Science*, 98(3), 520–532. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2014.05.022>
- 26) Lomiwes, D., Farouk, M. M., Wu, G., & Young, O. A. (2014). The development of meat tenderness is likely to be compartmentalised by ultimate pH. *Meat Science*, 96(1), 646–651. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.meatsci.2013.08.022>
- 27) Monin G. (1988). Evolution post-mortem du tissu musculaire ET conséquences sur les qualités de la viande de porc. *Journ. Rech. Porcine*, 20, 201-214.
- 28) Lawrie R.A. (1998) *Lawrie's Meat Science*. Wood head Publishing Series in Food Science and Technology, Cambridge, UK.
- 29) Kim S, Kim G, Moon C, Ko K, Choi Y, Choe J, Ryu Y. (2022). Effects of Aging Methods and Periods on Quality Characteristics of Beef. *Food Sci Anim Resour*. 42(6):953-967. doi: 10.5851/kosfa.2022.e63. Epub 2022 Nov 1. PMID: 36415581; PMCID: PMC9647182.
- 30) Fabre R, Dalzotto G, Perlo F, Bonato P, Teira G, Tisocco O (2018). Cooking method effect on Warner-Bratzler shear force of different beef muscles. *Meat Sci* 138: 10-14

- 31) Warren, K.E. and Kastner, C.L. (1992) A Comparison of Dry-Aged and Vacuum-Aged Beef Strip Loins. *Journal of Muscle Foods*, 3, 151-157.
- 32) Vieira, C., M. Y., Diaz, B., Martínez and GarciaCachan, M.D. (2009). Effect of frozen storage conditions (temperature and length of storage) on microbial and sensory quality of rustic crossbred beef at different stages of aging. *Meat Science* 83, 398–404
- 33) Jezek, Frantisek & Kameník, Josef & Macharáčková, Blanka & Králová, Kateřina & Bednář, Jiří. (2019). cooking of meat: effect on texture, cooking loss and microbiological quality – a review. *Acta Veterinaria Brno*. 88. 487-496. 10.2754/avb201988040487.
- 34) Warriss, P.D., (2000). *Meat Science: An Introductory Text*. CABI, UK.
- 35) Honikel, K.O., and R. Hamm. (1994) Measurement of water-holding capacity, and juiciness. In A.M. Pearson, and T.R. Dutson (Eds.), *Advances in Meat Research* (Vol. 9, pp. 125-161). Glasgow: Blackie Academic, and Professional.
- 36) Bendall, J. R., and J. Wismer-Pedersen, (1962). Some properties of the fibrillar proteins of normal and watery pork muscle. *J. Food Sci.* 27:144–159.
- 37) Ambrosiadis, I., Theodorakakos, N., Georgakis, S., & Lekas, S. (1994). Influence of thawing methods on the quality of frozen meat and the drip loss. *Fleischwirtschaft (Frankfurt)*, 74(3), 284-287.